

Sequence Distribution in Acrylonitrile-Methyl Methacrylate Copolymers by NMR Spectroscopy : Analysis of α -Methyl Peaks

A. K. KASHYAP and (Mrs.) V. KALPAGAM

Department of Inorganic & Physical Chemistry, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore-560012

Manuscript received 14 September 1976 ; accepted 15 January 1977

Complex pattern of α -methyl peaks of the NMR spectra of Acrylonitrile-Methyl Methacrylate Copolymers are analysed for sequence distribution analysis in order to understand the chain propagation mechanism in these copolymer systems.

THE properties of copolymers are generally affected not only by the average degree of polymerization and average composition, but also by the sequence distribution of the components and of their configuration in the copolymers. Most of the copolymerization systems have been successfully treated by the Mayo-Lewis equation¹, which postulates that only the terminal unit of a growing polymer chain affects the probability of monomer addition. Several cases of radical copolymerization have been reported which have failed to obey this assumption, particularly in case of monomers of high polarity such as acrylonitrile and fumaronitrile²⁻⁶. The existence of penultimate effect has been established from kinetical study of the radical copolymerization of acrylonitrile-methyl methacrylate⁷. This gives rise to pentad effects which results in the broadening of the two α -methyl singlets from syndiotactic and heterotactic triad sequences⁸⁻⁹. This kind of broadening of the α -methyl peaks has been reported for this copolymer system^{7,10}.

In our recent work on the sequence distribution of this copolymer system¹⁰, we have described the tentative assignment of various peaks with respect to the homopolymers in DMSO-d₆. We have found a very complicated pattern for the α -methyl peaks of the copolymers. These α -methyl peaks in the poly (methyl methacrylate) (PM) are very sensitive to the configurational effects of isotactic (i), heterotactic (h) and syndiotactic (s) triad sequences. In this paper, an attempt is made to analyze the α -methyl peaks to determine the microstructure of the copolymer chain.

Experimental

Acrylonitrile-methyl methacrylate copolymers (PAM) of four different compositions (MA₁-28.9 mole % of acrylonitrile (A), MA₂-41.5 mole % of A, MA₃-56.6 mole % of A and MA₄-65.7 mole % of A) were taken for the study. The methods of preparation of these copolymers along with other details have been described elsewhere¹¹. A tentative assignment of the various

peaks observed in a 100 MHz NMR spectra recorded in DMSO-d₆ has been reported in an earlier communication¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

In these spectra of the copolymers, three types of methyl methacrylate (M) centered triad sequences are expected to be present, namely, isolated M centered, AMA; 2 M centered AMM (or MMA) and 3M centered MMM triads. For A-rich copolymers, Pham⁷ found the presence of AMA and 2 M centered triad sequences based on his analysis of the methoxy and α -methyl peaks. However, he could not detect MMM sequences either by methoxy or α -methyl peaks. He further observed that the weight fraction of isolated M centered units i.e. AMA as observed by NMR was more than that calculated on the basis of kinetical analysis and 2M centered triads observed by NMR was less than that calculated on the basis of kinetical analysis. No peak was observed in the range 0.9-1.14 τ which corresponds to α -methyl peaks of pure PM, where the 3M sequences should have appeared, if it were present and could be detected by NMR for such a M-poor copolymer.

In our recent study¹⁰, on M-rich copolymers, we had indicated the presence of some peaks corresponding to s and h sequences of MMM type, besides the usual isolated M centered AMA and 2M centered MMA (or AMM) triads, based on the band shape of α -methyl peaks of the copolymer. In all these spectra, we find the presence of the peaks in the region where the peaks for PM appear (i.e. 8.78-9.11 τ). Therefore, it becomes very important to separate the M centered, 2M centered and 3M centered triad sequences before any meaningful conclusion could be drawn regarding the presence of M centered pentad sequences. This analysis has been done as follows.

The weight fraction of the PM sequences with nM units in the PAM copolymer has been calculated using

the following relation⁷ :

$$w'(n) = \frac{n P_{MMA}^2 \cdot P_{AMM} \cdot P_{MMM}^{n-3}}{P_{MMA} + P_{AMM}}$$

where P_{MMA} is the probability of addition of A monomer to a growing chain $-MM^{\circ}$, etc.

$$P_{MMA} = \frac{1}{1 + r_{MM} x_M}$$

$$P_{AMM} = \frac{r_{AM} x_M}{1 + r_{AM} x_M}$$

$$P_{AMA} = \frac{1}{1 + r_{AM} x_M}$$

$$\text{and, } P_{MMM} = \frac{r_{MM} x_M^2}{1 + r_{MM} x_M}$$

where $x_M = M/A$; the molar ratio of the initial mixture of monomers.

The reactivity ratios⁷ r_{MM} , r_{AM} , r_{AA} and r_{MA} are given as

$$r_{MM} = 1.01$$

$$r_{AM} = 1.56$$

$$r_{AA} = 0.39$$

$$\text{and } r_{MA} = 0.20$$

Table 1 gives the calculated % of M sequences with n unit lengths. It is evident from the table that all copolymers have sequences of 3 unit lengths and above, becoming less and less pronounced as we go from MA_1 to MA_4 .

In radical copolymerization of M-A system⁷, M monomer is consumed 2 or 3 times faster than the A monomer, thus AMA values calculated by kinetical

Fig. 1 α -methyl NMR Spectra at 100 MHz

TABLE 1—CALCULATED % (BY KINETICAL ANALYSIS) OF M SEQUENCES WITH n UNIT LENGTHS

Copolymer	x_M	w'(1)	w'(2)	w'(3)	w'(4)	w'(5)	w'(6)	w'(7)	w'(8)	w'(9)	w'(10)
MA_1	1.660	9.51	18.40	17.28	14.43	11.30	8.50	6.20	4.44	3.13	2.18
MA_2	0.748	23.72	31.54	20.36	11.69	6.29	3.25	1.63	0.78	0.49	0.18
MA_3	0.341	44.54	35.24	13.52	4.61	1.48	0.45	0.13	0.04	—	—
MA_4	0.187	60.95	30.00	7.18	1.56	0.30	0.06	—	—	—	—

It is seen that all the copolymers have 3M sequences and longer units. Therefore, the sequences of nM centered triad sequences, where $n \geq 3$, could be considered as 3M centered sequences w'(1) and w'(2) represent the % of M and 2M centered triad sequences.

Table 2 gives the % of these 3 types of sequences.

TABLE 2—CALCULATED % OF THE nM CENTERED TRIAD SEQUENCES.

Copolymer	AMA	AMM (or MMA)	MMM
MA_1	9.51	18.40	72.09
MA_2	23.72	31.54	44.74
MA_3	44.54	35.24	20.22
MA_4	60.95	30.00	9.05

analysis will be rather lower whereas 2M and 3M centered AMM (or MMA) and MMM values will be higher in actual case. As determined by NMR, the % of AMA will be higher than this value and % of 2M and 3M triad sequences will be lower than this value. Hence, Pham⁷ could not detect the 3M triad sequences for his M-poor copolymers, though he showed their presence by kinetical analysis.

Fig. 1 shows the α -methyl peaks of PM and all the copolymers on a single scale.

Due to the electronegativity of the substituent (CN) of the A units, the α -methyl peaks are shifted to lower magnetic fields^{1,2}. Therefore, it is possible to assume that the peaks at lower fields will contain more of A

(or less of M). In other words, as we proceed from low field to high field, the M centered, 2M centered and 3M centered sequences should appear. In the range 8.78-9.11 τ , all the 3 peaks, corresponding to i, h, s sequences of pure PM, could be assigned to 3M type (MMM) triad sequence. The peak at 8.75 τ (noticed as a small shoulder), slightly down field i type sequence could be assigned to a 2M type triad sequence of the type AMM (or MMA) only. The rest of the α -methyl peaks would then correspond to AMA type of sequences. This part of the spectrum is broad in case of MA₁, MA₂ and MA₃ which makes its further analysis impossible for an accurate estimation of pentad sequences. In case of MA₄, this peak is quite sharp and can be analyzed for its pentad sequences without much error. However, one important point has to be kept in mind that in the region 8.7-8.8 τ , there will be a considerable interplay between all the three types of M centered triad sequences, because it is very difficult to pinpoint the exact location of 2M sequences.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. P. Balram, Molecular Biophysics Unit, I.I.Sc. Bangalore for his keen interest in this work. Financial assistance from I.I.Sc., Bangalore is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. F. R. MAYO and F. M. LEWIS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1594.
2. W. G. BARB, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1953, **11**, 117.
3. G. E. HAM, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1954, **11**, 87.
4. G. E. HAM, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1960, **45**, 169.
5. G. E. HAM, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1960, **45**, 177.
6. G. E. HAM, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1962, **61**, 9.
7. Q. T. PHAM, "NMR—Basic Principles and Progress", Springer-Verlag, Berlin-Heidelberg, New York, 1971, Vol. 4, pp. 119-128.
8. KERNICT C. RAMEY, *J. Polym. Sci. B.*, 1967, **5**, 857.
9. R. C. FERGUSON, *Macromolecules.*, 1969, **2**, 237.
10. A.K. KASHYAP, RAMI C. REDDY and Mrs. V. KALPAGAM, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, **45**, 573.
11. A.K. KASHYAP, RAMI C. REDDY and Mrs. V. KALPAGAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 106.
12. J. GUILLOT, A. GUYOR and Q. T. PHAM, *J. Macromol Sci.*, A-2, 1968, **7**, 1303.